

propylene carbonate. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$) were calculated by Koutecky's method³⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

Ni(II), Co(II) and Ge(IV) give well-defined waves in the presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate. In the case of $UO_2(II)$, two waves of equal height are obtained in the absence of propylene carbonate but with the addition of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate the second wave gets obliterated. Since each wave of $UO_2(II)$ corresponds to a 1 electron reduction process, the reduction of $UO_2(II)$ in the presence of propylene carbonate takes place as : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$.

The waves of all the depolarizers are diffusion-controlled as revealed by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{O_2}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Various criteria of irreversibility⁷⁻¹⁰ indicate that the electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) are irreversible in the presence of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

The values of polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$) for the electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) have been calculated as a function of propylene carbonate.

Influence of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate on the kinetics of electrode reactions of Ni(II), Co(II), $UO_2(II)$ and Ge(IV) :

(i) *Electrode reactions of Ni(II) and Co(II) :* It has been found that both αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ decrease with increasing amounts (0-20%) of propylene carbonate. It follows from this that the electrode reactions of Ni(II) and Co(II) are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

(ii) *Electrode reaction of $UO_2(II)$:* Each reduction step of $UO_2(II)$ in 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ (in the absence of propylene carbonate) corresponds to 1 electron reduction wave : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$ and $UO_2^+ + e \rightarrow UO_2$. The single reduction step occurring in the presence of aqueous mixtures of propylene carbonate corresponds to the reduction of UO_2^{2+} to UO_2^+ as this step appears at more positive potentials.

With the addition of 4% (v/v) propylene carbonate both αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ tend to increase thereby suggesting that the electrode reaction : $UO_2^{2+} + e \rightarrow UO_2^+$ becomes less irreversible. However, further increase (6-20%) of the percentage of propylene carbonate in aqueous mixture renders the above electrode reaction more irreversible as evidenced by the decreasing value of αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$.

(iii) *Electrode reaction of Ge(IV) :* It has been found that with the addition of increasing amounts (0-20%) of propylene carbonate, the kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k^{\circ}_{t,h}$ tend to decrease. This implies

that the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) is rendered more irreversible with the addition of increasing amounts of propylene carbonate.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Principal, Agra College, Agra for research facilities.

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Synthesis of Some Substituted Phenylalkylamines

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Manuscript received 8 August 1980, revised 2 May 1981, accepted 1 October 1981

SUBSTITUTED phenylalkylamines have been synthesised as antiamoebic agents and the retention of the dimethoxy moiety was generally regarded as essential for the maintenance of the activity¹⁻⁷.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of some α -(2-ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl) ethylamines (Scheme 1) and β -(2-ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl) ethylamines (Scheme 2).

R : a, Et : b ; n-Pr : c ; n-Bu

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. $^1\text{H NMR}$ was recorded with TMS as internal standard and chemical shifts are reported in δ (ppm) units.

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylacetophenones (II) : 2, 4-Dihydroxy-5-alkylacetophenones (I) were prepared by the usual Nencki reaction of 4-alkylresorcinols. These were monomethylated by refluxing with dimethylsulphate (1.1 mol) and ignited K_2CO_3 (2 mol) in dry acetone for 3 hr. After usual working up, the 4-methoxy-2-hydroxy-5-alkylacetophenones were ethylated by refluxing with diethylsulphate (1.1 mol) and ignited K_2CO_3 (2 mol) in dry acetone for 36 hr. The ketones were crystallized from ethylacetate-pet. ether as white solids. m.p. IIa, 81-2° ; IIb, 78-9° ; IIc, 65-6° . UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm :

312, 260 and 230. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 1665, 1600, 1570, 1505, 1350, 1330, 1265, 1230, 1205, 1170, 1110, 1045, 915 and 820. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 1.0-1.2 (t, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.50 (t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ and m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.53 (s, $-\text{COCH}_3$ and t, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-$), 3.96 (s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.16 (q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.3 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.53 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$).

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylacetophenone oximes (III) : II were converted into the oximes with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and sodium acetate by the usual procedure ; crystallized from aq. alcohol as white needles. m.p. IIIa, 141-42° ; IIIb, 114-15° ; IIIc, 95-6° . UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm : 280, 230 and 208. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 3260-3210 (b), 1605, 1500, 1465, 1320, 1200, 1155, 1045, 1005, 930, 890 and 810. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 2.16 (s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 6.33 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.13 (1H, s,

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 NOH
 $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$, $\text{D}_2\text{O} \times \text{ge}$ 4.6 (1H, =NOH).

α -(2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl)ethylamine (IV) : III were reduced by refluxing with zinc dust, ammonium acetate, liquor ammonia and alcohol by the known procedure⁸. The ethereal solution of the amines was dried over anh. Na_2SO_4 and KOH. Dry HCl was passed through it when the amine hydrochlorides separated as white solids ;

crystallized from MeOH-EtOAc as white shining solids. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 3020-2870 (b), 1505, 1580, 1505, 1470, 1290, 1200, 1120, 1050, 915 and 810. 3020-2870 (b, N-H stretching vibrations), 1580 and 1505 (N-H bending vibrations). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (TFA) : δ 1.0-1.66 (m, $-\text{CH}_2$ and $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$). 2.6 (t, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-$), 4.0 (s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.2 (q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.70 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.13 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$).

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes (VI) : These were prepared by the formylation of 4-ethoxy-2-methoxyalkylbenzenes (V) with 1 : 1 complex of DMF (0.5 mol) and POCl_3 (0.5 mol) with protection from moisture by the known procedure⁹. The benzaldehydes were crystallized from light petroleum as white flaky solids. m. p. Va, 81-2° ; Vb, 77-8° ; Vc, 50-1° , UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm : 326, 272, 232.

IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 2870, 2760, 1665, 1605, 1320, 1260, 1110, 1045, 910 and 815. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 1.0-1.2 (t, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.50 (t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ and m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.56 (t, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-$), 3.96 (s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.13 (q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.30 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.6 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 10.0 ($-\text{CH}=\text{O}$).

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkyl- β -nitrostyrenes (VII) : VI were condensed with nitromethane (1.1 mol) in presence of ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid under anhydrous conditions by the known procedure^{10,11}. The nitrostyrenes were crystallized from methanol as yellow needles. m.p. VIIa, 84-5° ; VIIb, 100-1° , VIIc, 69-70° . UV $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm :

380, 316, 274 and 236. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 3140, 1610, 1510, 1490, 1335, 1265, 1120, 1045, 970 and 815. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 6.33 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.1 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.6 (1H, d, $J=14.0$ Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{NO}_2$), 7.96 (1H, d, $J=14.0$ Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{NO}_2$).

β -(2-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-5-alkylphenyl)ethylamines (VIII) : VII were reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in anhydrous ether by the known procedure^{12,13}. Excess of LAH was destroyed by dropwise addition of 15% NaOH. The ethereal layer was dried over anh. Na_2SO_4 and KOH, and dry HCl passed through it when the amine hydrochloride separated ; crystallized from MeOH-EtOAc as white shining flaky solids. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 3020-2840 (b), 1605, 1580, 1510, 1470, 1290, 1200, 1120, 1045, 910 and 810. 3020-2840 (b, N-H stretching vibrations) 1580 and 1510 (N-H bending vibrations). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (TFA) : δ 1.0-1.2 (t, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.50 (t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ and m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.56 (t, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-$), 3.13 (t, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 3.50 (m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 4.0 (s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.20 (q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.70 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.0 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$).

Bioassay: The amine hydrochlorides were screened *in vitro* for amoebicidal activity against axenically grown *E. histolytica*. Their activity is reported in the Table 1. The substituted β -phenylethylamines are more active than the corresponding α -phenylethylamines and the 2-ethoxy-4-methoxy compounds more than the corresponding 2,4-dimethoxy compounds.

TABLE 1— α AND β -(2-ETHOXY-4-METHOXY-5-ALKYLPHENYL)ETHYLAMINE HYDROCHLORIDES AND THEIR AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY

Compound	R	m.p.	% Found (Calcd.)			Amoebicidal activity $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (min. inhib conc)
			O	H	N	
IVa	Et	203-10°	60.10 (60.19)	8.44 (8.48)	5.32 (5.39)	NA ⁺
IVb	<i>n</i> -Pr	194°	61.36 (61.42)	8.72 (8.77)	5.06 (5.12)	500
IVc	<i>n</i> -Bu	180°	62.56 (62.61)	9.02 (9.01)	4.83 (4.87)	500
VIIa	Et	218°	60.14 (60.19)	8.46 (8.48)	5.43 (5.39)	250
VIIb	<i>n</i> -Pr	212-3°	61.40 (61.43)	8.76 (8.77)	5.04 (5.12)	125
VIIIc	<i>n</i> -Bu	155-6°	62.73 (62.61)	9.10 (9.03)	4.86 (4.87)	62.5

* NA = Non-active.

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Synthesis of Steroidal Spirothiazolidinones : Reaction of 5 α -Cholestane-3,6-dione with β -Mercaptoacetic Acid

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Manuscript received 3 August 1981, accepted 6 November 1981

SPIROTHIAZOLIDINONES have been reported to have pharmacological activities such as anaesthetic¹, antibiotic² and amoebicidal³. These observations prompted us to undertake the synthesis of steroidal spirothiazolidinones⁴. This note

is concerned with the reaction of 5 α -cholestane-3,6-dione(I) with β -mercaptoacetic acid (BF₃-etherate as catalyst) which afforded isomeric steroidal spirothiazolidinones, S-spiro(5 α -cholestan-6-one-3,2')thiazolidinone-4'(II) and R-spiro(5 α -cholestan-6-one-3,2')thiazolidinone-4'(III). The structure of these compounds was established on the basis of ¹H nmr data.

Experimental

The dione (I)⁵ (1.50 g), β -mercaptoacetic acid (3.4 g, 10 mole excess), ammonium carbonate (3.6 g) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 32 hr in Dean and Stark apparatus. At the end of the reaction, the benzene solution was washed with water, 1N sodium hydroxide solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and chromatographed over silica gel (30.0 g). Elution with benzene-ether (8 : 1) furnished the compound (II) (0.37 g), m.p. 262°; Found: C, 73.4; H, 9.88; N, 2.93; S, 6.73. C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S requires C, 73.57; H, 9.93; N, 2.96; S, 6.76%. IR: ν_{max} 3140, 3060

cm⁻¹ (—NH—), 1710 (—C—), 1690 (—NH—C—), 1420

cm⁻¹ (—CN), ¹H nmr: δ 8.10 brs (—NH—C—), 3.63 s (—C—CH₂—S—), 0.92 (C₁₀—CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈—CH₃), 0.83 and 0.78 (other methyl protons).

Further elution with benzene-ether (6 : 1) yielded (III), recrystallized from light petroleum (0.45 g), m.p. 295°; Found: C, 73.41; H, 9.89; N, 2.43; S, 6.74. C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S requires C, 73.57; H, 9.93; N,

2.96; S, 6.76%. IR: ν_{max} 3140, 3060 (—NH—C—), 1710 (—C—), 1690 (—NH—C—), 1429 cm⁻¹ (—CN)

¹H nmr δ 8.10 br (—NH—C—), 3.53 s (—C—CH₂—S), 0.92 (C₁₀—CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈—CH₃), 0.83 and 0.78 (other methyl protons).

Results and Discussion

The compounds (II) and (III) analysed for C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S are isomeric. The ir spectra of (II)